

FLOATECH

D2.1. Aero-Hydro-Elastic Model Definition in QBlade Ocean

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FLOATECH
THE FUTURE OF FLOATING WIND TURBINES

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Background: about the FLOATECH project

The FLOATECH project is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union's H2020 programme aiming to increase the technical maturity and the cost competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) energy. This is particularly important because, due to the limitations of available installation sites onshore, offshore wind is becoming crucial to ensure the further growth of the wind energy sector.

The project is implemented by a European consortium of 5 public research institutions with relevant skills in the field of offshore floating wind energy and 3 industrial partners, two of which have been involved in the most recent developments of floating wind systems.

The approach of FLOATECH can be broken down into three actions:

- The development, implementation and validation of a user-friendly and efficient design engineering tool (named QBlade-Ocean) performing simulations of floating offshore wind turbines with an unseen combination of aerodynamic and hydrodynamic fidelity. The advanced modelling theories will lead to a reduction of the uncertainties in the design process and an increase of turbine efficiency.
- The development of two innovative control techniques (i.e. Active Wave-based feed-forward Control and the Active Wake Mixing) for floating wind turbines and floaters, combining wave prediction and anticipation of induced platform motions. This is expected to improve the performance of each machine and to minimise wake effects in floating wind farms, leading to a net increase in the annual energy production of the farm.
- The economic analysis of these concepts to demonstrate qualitatively and quantitatively the impact of the developed technologies on the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of FOW technology.

In addition to the technological and economic impacts, the project is expected to have several impacts at societal, environmental and political levels, such as: public acceptance due to reduced noise and visibility issues of FOWT; very low impact on biodiversity and wildlife habitat because no piles are needed to be installed into the seabed; design choices requiring less material and space; the promotion of the installation of FOW in transitional water depths (30-50 meters), as the costs for FOW at those locations will become more competitive compared to the fixed bottom foundations.

Table of contents

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. INTRODUCTION	6
1.1. CONTEXT WITHIN FLOATECH	6
1.2. DOCUMENT STRUCTURE	6
2. SOFTWIND 10 MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE	7
2.1. MODEL DEFINITION	7
2.1.1. <i>Blade</i>	8
2.1.2. <i>Nacelle and Tower</i>	13
2.1.3. <i>Substructure</i>	14
2.1.4. <i>Mooring System</i>	15
2.2. PRELIMINARY VALIDATION	15
2.2.1. <i>Frequency Calculations</i>	15
2.2.2. <i>Decay Tests</i>	16
2.3. PUBLIC LOCATION OF THE MODEL	19
3. DTU 10 MW RTW WITH HEXAFLOAT SUBSTRUCTURE	20
3.1. MODEL DEFINITION	20
3.1.1. <i>Blade</i>	21
3.1.2. <i>Nacelle and Tower</i>	21
3.1.3. <i>Substructure</i>	23
3.1.4. <i>Mooring System</i>	25
3.2. PRELIMINARY VALIDATION	25
3.2.1. <i>Frequency Calculations</i>	25
3.2.2. <i>Decay tests</i>	27
3.3. PUBLIC LOCATION OF THE MODEL	28
4. OC5 5MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE	28
4.1. MODEL DEFINITION	29
4.1.1. <i>Blade</i>	30
4.1.2. <i>Nacelle and Tower</i>	32
4.1.3. <i>Substructure</i>	34
4.1.4. <i>Mooring System</i>	35
4.2. PRELIMINARY VALIDATION	36
4.2.1. <i>Frequency Calculations</i>	36
4.2.2. <i>Static Tests</i>	37
4.2.3. <i>Decay Tests</i>	37
4.3. PUBLIC LOCATION OF THE MODEL	39
5. REFERENCES	39

List of acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CoM	Centre of Mass
CW	Counter Weight
DoF	Degree of Freedom
EF	Eigenfrequency
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
LPMD	Linear Potential Morison Drag
ME	Morison Equation
MSWT	Marin Stock Wind Turbine
IP	In-plane
OOP	Out-of-plane
RNA	Rotor-Nacelle Assembly
RWT	Reference Wind Turbine
QB	QBlade Ocean
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a report accompanying the deliverable 2.1 of the FLOATECH project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007142.

For the detailed validation and verification of the capabilities of QBlade Ocean (QB) in work package 2, a detailed definition of the models is needed. This document presents the three aero-hydro-elastic models that will be used for this validation. These include two models for experimental validation: the upscaled 10 MW SOFTWIND experimental turbine mounted on a spar floater and the upscaled 5 MW OC5 experimental turbine mounted on a semi-submersible floater. The third model – the DTU 10MW Reference Wind Turbine mounted on the Hexafloat floater – is used for numerical validation against the established commercial code DeepLines Wind™.

This document includes the definition of each of the three models and the results of the preliminary tests performed to validate the model behaviour. A link to the database is provided where the full QBlade Ocean model definition will be available.

1. INTRODUCTION

The context within the FLOATECH project is first outlined, followed by a brief overview of the structure of the document.

1.1. CONTEXT WITHIN FLOATECH

This document presents the aero-hydro-elastic models in QB that will be used in Task 2.1 of Work Package 2. They are three models with different rated power and floater geometries: the 10 MW SOFTWIND turbine mounted on a spar floater, the 5 MW OC5 turbine mounted on a semi-submersible floater and the DTU 10 MW Reference Wind Turbine mounted on the Hexafloat floater. These three models will be used for the verification and validation of the capabilities of QB within Task 2.1. Furthermore, they will be slightly adapted and used for Task 2.2 of Work Package 2. Each model represents a different approach of FOWT technology and it is essential that the aero-hydro-elastic capabilities of QB are verified with a broad range of designs to ensure that the software can be used for all types of FOWTs. The QB models will be made available to the public so that researchers and industrial developers can use them in future follow-up studies.

1.2. DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The document is divided into three sections. In each section, the aero-hydro-elastic definition of one model is given, along with the results of a set of preliminary validation tests. Finally,

each section also contains the link to the online database that will include the QB model of the FOWT.

2. SOFTWIND 10 MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE

This section includes the definition and results of preliminary validation tests of the SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT mounted on a spar buoy.

2.1. MODEL DEFINITION

The detailed model definition is given in [1]. In this document we only give a summary of the most important aero-hydro-elastic properties of the SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT model. Figure 1 shows the aero-hydro-elastic model of the FOWT as modelled in QB. The main parameters of the model are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: General parameters of the SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT.

Parameter	Value
Rated power	10 MW
Number of blades	3
Rotor diameter	178.3 m
Nominal hub height	121.3 m
Nominal draft	90 m
Rated rotor speed	9.6 rpm
Overhang	7.1 m
Shaft tilt angle	5 deg
Rotor pre-cone angle	2.5 deg
RNA mass	$8.0 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Tower mass	$1.603 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Substructure total mass	$2.019 \cdot 10^7$ kg

Figure 1: SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT aero-hydro-elastic model in QB.

2.1.1. Blade

The rotor of the SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT is based on the DTU 10 MW reference wind turbine [2]. The detailed aerodynamic definition, including the airfoil polar data, as well as the structural definition of the blades are given in this reference. Table 2 shows the aerodynamic definition of the DTU 10 MW RWT blade within QB.

Table 2: Aerodynamic blade definition of the SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT

Position [m]	Chord [m]	Twist [deg]	IP Offset [m]	OOP Offset [m]	Thread Axis [-]	Airfoil
2.8	5.38	14.5	0	0.0001	0.5	t100.0_dtu_10mw_Cylinder.txt
4.8038	5.38	14.5	0	-0.0081	0.5	t100.0_dtu_10mw_Cylinder.txt
7.521	5.38	14.5	0.0042	-0.0195	0.5	t96.9_dtu_10mw_t96.9_Interpolated.txt
8.2063	5.38	14.5	0.0059	-0.0224	0.5	t95.3_dtu_10mw_t95.3_Interpolated.txt
9.131	5.3886	14.5	0.0111	-0.0257	0.5	t92.7_dtu_10mw_t92.7_Interpolated.txt
10.2891	5.4212	14.4425	0.029	-0.0276	0.5	t88.8_dtu_10mw_t88.8_Interpolated.txt
11.6744	5.4865	14.2692	0.0616	-0.0275	0.5	t83.4_dtu_10mw_t83.4_Interpolated.txt
13.2759	5.5887	13.9747	0.1312	-0.0209	0.5	t76.7_dtu_10mw_t76.7_Interpolated.txt
15.0866	5.7247	13.3567	0.2315	-0.0124	0.5	t68.8_dtu_10mw_t68.8_Interpolated.txt
17.0936	5.8817	12.2925	0.3558	-0.006	0.5	t60.3_dtu_10mw_t60.3_Interpolated.txt
19.2861	6.0346	11.0083	0.4817	-0.011	0.5	t52.3_dtu_10mw_t52.3_Interpolated.txt
21.6534	6.1478	9.6676	0.6035	-0.0246	0.5	t45.8_dtu_10mw_t45.8_Interpolated.txt
24.1791	6.202	8.46	0.7062	-0.05	0.5	t41.0_dtu_10mw_t41.0_Interpolated.txt
26.85	6.195	7.6301	0.7766	-0.0866	0.5	t37.3_dtu_10mw_t37.3_Interpolated.txt
29.6486	6.1292	6.947	0.8233	-0.1327	0.5	t34.5_dtu_10mw_t34.5_Interpolated.txt

32.5575	6.0096	6.3385	0.8474	-0.1894	0.5	t32.3_dtu_10mw_t32.3_Interpolated.txt
35.5605	5.8432	5.7599	0.8512	-0.2568	0.5	t30.5_dtu_10mw_t30.5_Interpolated.txt
38.6372	5.64	5.1898	0.834	-0.3379	0.5	t29.0_dtu_10mw_t29.0_Interpolated.txt
41.7708	5.4107	4.6154	0.8053	-0.4278	0.5	t27.8_dtu_10mw_t27.8_Interpolated.txt
44.941	5.1613	3.9957	0.7703	-0.5312	0.5	t26.7_dtu_10mw_t26.7_Interpolated.txt
48.1309	4.8974	3.3478	0.7315	-0.6434	0.5	t25.8_dtu_10mw_t25.8_Interpolated.txt
51.3192	4.6255	2.6912	0.6914	-0.7696	0.5	t25.2_dtu_10mw_t25.2_Interpolated.txt
54.4882	4.3519	2.0326	0.6508	-0.9042	0.5	t24.7_dtu_10mw_t24.7_Interpolated.txt
57.6175	4.0827	1.4025	0.611	-1.0509	0.5	t24.3_dtu_10mw_t24.3_Interpolated.txt
60.6893	3.822	0.7982	0.5721	-1.2045	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
63.6853	3.5724	0.245	0.5349	-1.3682	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
66.5866	3.3364	-0.255	0.4995	-1.5405	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
69.3762	3.1161	-0.7182	0.4663	-1.7146	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
72.0366	2.913	-1.1164	0.4363	-1.9016	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
74.5541	2.7275	-1.4933	0.408	-2.0786	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
76.9111	2.5595	-1.8298	0.3825	-2.2646	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
79.0951	2.4087	-2.1381	0.359	-2.4412	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
81.0923	2.266	-2.4201	0.3376	-2.6028	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
82.8922	2.1175	-2.6729	0.3154	-2.7547	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
84.4824	1.9588	-2.8877	0.2919	-2.9004	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
85.8538	1.7913	-3.0635	0.2652	-3.0284	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
86.9996	1.6013	-3.1993	0.2336	-3.1353	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
87.9116	1.3858	-3.3012	0.1986	-3.2204	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
88.5836	1.1384	-3.3684	0.1419	-3.2828	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt
89.2	0.8335	-3.43	0.0899	-3.34	0.5	t24.1_dtu_10mw_FFA-W3-241_(Re=12x10^6).txt

The experimental setup of the SOFTWIND turbine consisted of a thrust actuator with a software-in-the-loop aerodynamic model coupled to a physical tower and floater [1]. To increase computational efficiency and allow real-time calculation of the aerodynamic thrust, the number of nodes where the aerodynamic forces are calculated were reduced to 18 in the experiments. To avoid discrepancies arising from different accuracies used in QB and in the experimental setup, the aerodynamic definition presented in Table 2 was interpolated to 18 panels in QB. The panels were chosen to have a cosine spacing to increase the resolution at the blade root and tip. An equivalent approach was also followed in [1]. The panel distribution in QB can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2 : Aerodynamic panel distribution of the SOFTWIND rotor in QB.

Table 3 and Table 4 show the structural definition of the blade. The detailed definition of the column entries can be found in [3].

Table 3: Structural definition of the DTU 10 MW RWT blade in QB.

Norm. Length [-]	Mass Dens. [kg/m ³]	Edge Stiff. [N m ²]	Flap Stiff. [N m ²]	Axial Stiff. [N]	Tors. Stiff. [N m ²]	Shear Stiff [N]	Struc. Pitch [deg]	Shear Factor X [-]
0.000E+00	1.190E+03	6.187E+10	6.101E+10	1.779E+10	2.746E+10	3.563E+09	0.000E+00	5.452E-01
2.333E-02	1.192E+03	6.218E+10	6.112E+10	1.784E+10	2.748E+10	3.567E+09	0.000E+00	5.457E-01
4.333E-02	1.203E+03	6.300E+10	6.113E+10	1.808E+10	2.732E+10	3.584E+09	0.000E+00	5.505E-01
6.333E-02	1.172E+03	6.015E+10	5.809E+10	1.766E+10	2.560E+10	3.480E+09	0.000E+00	5.614E-01
8.333E-02	1.114E+03	5.456E+10	5.305E+10	1.685E+10	2.214E+10	3.252E+09	0.000E+00	5.701E-01
1.033E-01	1.049E+03	4.410E+10	5.086E+10	1.596E+10	1.839E+10	3.041E+09	-4.280E+01	5.857E-01
1.233E-01	9.746E+02	3.579E+10	4.394E+10	1.483E+10	1.397E+10	2.775E+09	-3.591E+01	5.939E-01
1.433E-01	9.087E+02	2.839E+10	3.787E+10	1.385E+10	1.010E+10	2.554E+09	-2.574E+01	5.914E-01
1.633E-01	8.689E+02	2.269E+10	3.377E+10	1.326E+10	7.448E+09	2.427E+09	-1.893E+01	5.954E-01
1.800E-01	8.455E+02	1.912E+10	3.177E+10	1.290E+10	6.028E+09	2.393E+09	-1.428E+01	6.127E-01
2.049E-01	7.752E+02	1.479E+10	2.750E+10	1.169E+10	4.052E+09	2.154E+09	-1.097E+01	5.780E-01
2.250E-01	7.358E+02	1.266E+10	2.538E+10	1.101E+10	3.351E+09	2.039E+09	-8.868E+00	5.430E-01
2.450E-01	6.911E+02	1.081E+10	2.293E+10	1.027E+10	2.638E+09	1.899E+09	-7.622E+00	4.980E-01
2.650E-01	6.549E+02	9.333E+09	2.065E+10	9.659E+09	2.119E+09	1.785E+09	-6.790E+00	4.561E-01
2.850E-01	6.259E+02	8.139E+09	1.877E+10	9.185E+09	1.744E+09	1.698E+09	-6.090E+00	4.226E-01
3.050E-01	5.933E+02	6.883E+09	1.875E+10	8.712E+09	1.419E+09	1.604E+09	-4.893E+00	3.823E-01
3.250E-01	5.810E+02	6.093E+09	1.766E+10	8.557E+09	1.243E+09	1.572E+09	-4.530E+00	3.827E-01
3.450E-01	5.662E+02	5.397E+09	1.651E+10	8.383E+09	1.090E+09	1.531E+09	-4.252E+00	3.754E-01
3.650E-01	5.482E+02	4.798E+09	1.505E+10	8.192E+09	9.619E+08	1.490E+09	-4.103E+00	3.789E-01
3.850E-01	5.297E+02	4.261E+09	1.354E+10	7.953E+09	8.335E+08	1.436E+09	-3.926E+00	3.738E-01
4.050E-01	5.103E+02	3.791E+09	1.243E+10	7.764E+09	7.445E+08	1.397E+09	-3.651E+00	3.763E-01
4.250E-01	4.947E+02	3.350E+09	1.148E+10	7.555E+09	6.544E+08	1.356E+09	-3.350E+00	3.780E-01
4.450E-01	4.775E+02	2.955E+09	1.044E+10	7.328E+09	5.708E+08	1.306E+09	-3.092E+00	3.708E-01
4.640E-01	4.609E+02	2.618E+09	9.468E+09	7.109E+09	5.029E+08	1.263E+09	-2.886E+00	3.734E-01
4.840E-01	4.418E+02	2.296E+09	8.503E+09	6.853E+09	4.432E+08	1.214E+09	-2.646E+00	3.785E-01
5.040E-01	4.253E+02	2.014E+09	7.704E+09	6.624E+09	3.918E+08	1.171E+09	-2.411E+00	3.813E-01
5.240E-01	4.014E+02	1.757E+09	6.644E+09	6.308E+09	3.379E+08	1.107E+09	-2.255E+00	3.775E-01

5.440E-01	3.851E+02	1.535E+09	5.973E+09	6.059E+09	2.971E+08	1.063E+09	-2.047E+00	3.811E-01
5.640E-01	3.660E+02	1.346E+09	5.329E+09	5.824E+09	2.640E+08	1.020E+09	-1.855E+00	3.848E-01
5.840E-01	3.469E+02	1.169E+09	4.669E+09	5.530E+09	2.252E+08	9.623E+08	-1.696E+00	3.795E-01
6.050E-01	3.263E+02	1.015E+09	3.991E+09	5.252E+09	1.985E+08	9.147E+08	-1.563E+00	3.839E-01
6.250E-01	3.103E+02	8.854E+08	3.540E+09	5.007E+09	1.748E+08	8.719E+08	-1.418E+00	3.887E-01
6.450E-01	2.917E+02	7.715E+08	3.050E+09	4.738E+09	1.524E+08	8.227E+08	-1.289E+00	3.813E-01
6.650E-01	2.724E+02	6.684E+08	2.616E+09	4.451E+09	1.326E+08	7.736E+08	-1.187E+00	3.869E-01
6.850E-01	2.570E+02	5.781E+08	2.271E+09	4.185E+09	1.165E+08	7.305E+08	-1.095E+00	3.940E-01
7.050E-01	2.378E+02	4.995E+08	1.922E+09	3.902E+09	1.014E+08	6.836E+08	-9.948E-01	3.876E-01
7.243E-01	2.218E+02	4.292E+08	1.667E+09	3.635E+09	8.916E+07	6.394E+08	-9.215E-01	3.973E-01
7.443E-01	2.032E+02	3.632E+08	1.393E+09	3.337E+09	7.701E+07	5.890E+08	-8.653E-01	4.077E-01
7.643E-01	1.868E+02	3.048E+08	1.185E+09	3.050E+09	6.562E+07	5.403E+08	-7.819E-01	4.072E-01
7.843E-01	1.717E+02	2.539E+08	9.976E+08	2.776E+09	5.673E+07	4.980E+08	-7.408E-01	4.206E-01
8.050E-01	1.538E+02	2.082E+08	8.150E+08	2.489E+09	4.799E+07	4.494E+08	-6.721E-01	4.238E-01
8.250E-01	1.401E+02	1.710E+08	6.850E+08	2.244E+09	4.147E+07	4.154E+08	-6.491E-01	4.364E-01
8.450E-01	1.244E+02	1.381E+08	5.540E+08	1.981E+09	3.568E+07	3.764E+08	-5.994E-01	4.645E-01
8.644E-01	1.089E+02	1.087E+08	4.607E+08	1.720E+09	2.899E+07	3.295E+08	-5.742E-01	4.661E-01
8.844E-01	9.518E+01	8.394E+07	3.591E+08	1.467E+09	2.390E+07	2.899E+08	-5.385E-01	4.931E-01
9.050E-01	8.234E+01	6.306E+07	2.961E+08	1.250E+09	2.025E+07	2.597E+08	-5.722E-01	5.370E-01
9.250E-01	6.828E+01	4.428E+07	2.172E+08	1.007E+09	1.554E+07	2.178E+08	-5.475E-01	5.657E-01
9.446E-01	5.447E+01	2.834E+07	1.550E+08	7.791E+08	1.139E+07	1.788E+08	-5.934E-01	6.174E-01
9.650E-01	4.065E+01	1.448E+07	1.004E+08	5.539E+08	7.214E+06	1.390E+08	-6.878E-01	6.760E-01
9.850E-01	2.520E+01	4.497E+06	4.172E+07	3.074E+08	2.936E+06	9.023E+07	-7.933E-01	7.166E-01
1.000E+00	1.542E+01	1.028E+06	1.271E+07	1.722E+08	7.933E+05	5.633E+07	-9.549E-01	6.856E-01

Table 4: Structural definition of the DTU 10 MW RWT blade in QB (continued).

Norm. Length [-]	Shear Factor Y [-]	Rad. Gyr. X [-]	Rad. Gyr. Y [-]	Center Mass X [-]	Center Mass Y [-]	Center Elast. X [-]	Center Elast. Y [-]	Center Shear X [-]	Center Shear Y [-]
0.000E+00	7.039E-01	3.390E-01	3.281E-01	-7.804E-04	-6.517E-04	-9.045E-04	-6.004E-04	-5.371E-04	-1.758E-03
2.333E-02	7.030E-01	3.392E-01	3.281E-01	-1.012E-03	-6.777E-04	-1.166E-03	-6.133E-04	-6.651E-04	-1.785E-03
4.333E-02	6.937E-01	3.382E-01	3.271E-01	-2.186E-03	-1.059E-03	-1.139E-03	-7.644E-04	-2.968E-04	-1.576E-03
6.333E-02	6.739E-01	3.332E-01	3.248E-01	-3.213E-03	-1.005E-03	-2.986E-03	-8.307E-04	1.162E-03	9.208E-04
8.333E-02	6.404E-01	3.206E-01	3.180E-01	-2.634E-04	-1.521E-03	2.500E-03	-9.690E-04	6.905E-03	2.053E-03
1.033E-01	5.847E-01	2.948E-01	3.132E-01	3.490E-03	-6.627E-04	7.441E-03	4.570E-04	2.043E-02	6.751E-03
1.233E-01	5.246E-01	2.702E-01	2.973E-01	1.751E-02	7.073E-04	2.436E-02	1.440E-03	5.191E-02	1.204E-02
1.433E-01	4.599E-01	2.414E-01	2.846E-01	2.724E-02	2.168E-03	3.560E-02	1.917E-03	8.709E-02	1.747E-02
1.633E-01	4.071E-01	2.130E-01	2.740E-01	4.334E-02	3.760E-03	5.289E-02	2.798E-03	1.285E-01	1.559E-02
1.800E-01	3.636E-01	1.933E-01	2.680E-01	5.389E-02	5.110E-03	6.464E-02	3.809E-03	1.565E-01	1.609E-02
2.049E-01	3.367E-01	1.725E-01	2.613E-01	6.321E-02	5.242E-03	7.938E-02	3.558E-03	1.788E-01	1.701E-02
2.250E-01	3.334E-01	1.612E-01	2.595E-01	6.906E-02	6.181E-03	8.935E-02	4.653E-03	1.773E-01	1.984E-02
2.450E-01	3.245E-01	1.525E-01	2.561E-01	7.762E-02	6.673E-03	1.002E-01	5.392E-03	1.890E-01	1.976E-02
2.650E-01	3.193E-01	1.454E-01	2.537E-01	8.659E-02	6.799E-03	1.124E-01	5.705E-03	1.997E-01	1.903E-02
2.850E-01	3.160E-01	1.392E-01	2.512E-01	9.477E-02	6.581E-03	1.228E-01	5.586E-03	2.084E-01	1.814E-02
3.050E-01	3.129E-01	1.324E-01	2.547E-01	9.367E-02	6.008E-03	1.196E-01	5.009E-03	2.140E-01	1.603E-02
3.250E-01	3.091E-01	1.270E-01	2.526E-01	9.684E-02	4.898E-03	1.240E-01	3.866E-03	2.154E-01	1.388E-02
3.450E-01	3.042E-01	1.222E-01	2.502E-01	1.010E-01	3.878E-03	1.286E-01	2.789E-03	2.200E-01	1.205E-02
3.650E-01	2.991E-01	1.186E-01	2.475E-01	1.034E-01	3.237E-03	1.338E-01	2.091E-03	2.213E-01	1.065E-02

3.850E-01	2.925E-01	1.155E-01	2.442E-01	1.079E-01	3.015E-03	1.394E-01	1.827E-03	2.233E-01	1.019E-02
4.050E-01	2.852E-01	1.128E-01	2.423E-01	1.113E-01	3.073E-03	1.422E-01	1.886E-03	2.247E-01	1.011E-02
4.250E-01	2.777E-01	1.099E-01	2.411E-01	1.115E-01	3.326E-03	1.425E-01	2.129E-03	2.240E-01	1.037E-02
4.450E-01	2.729E-01	1.073E-01	2.390E-01	1.132E-01	3.634E-03	1.438E-01	2.430E-03	2.250E-01	1.080E-02
4.640E-01	2.674E-01	1.050E-01	2.381E-01	1.127E-01	4.041E-03	1.444E-01	2.818E-03	2.236E-01	1.116E-02
4.840E-01	2.593E-01	1.029E-01	2.361E-01	1.129E-01	4.483E-03	1.455E-01	3.263E-03	2.235E-01	1.167E-02
5.040E-01	2.551E-01	1.009E-01	2.359E-01	1.124E-01	4.966E-03	1.458E-01	3.740E-03	2.236E-01	1.212E-02
5.240E-01	2.551E-01	9.956E-02	2.315E-01	1.173E-01	5.302E-03	1.491E-01	4.126E-03	2.232E-01	1.268E-02
5.440E-01	2.481E-01	9.789E-02	2.315E-01	1.166E-01	5.745E-03	1.490E-01	4.571E-03	2.232E-01	1.308E-02
5.640E-01	2.467E-01	9.677E-02	2.298E-01	1.189E-01	6.072E-03	1.496E-01	4.943E-03	2.231E-01	1.352E-02
5.840E-01	2.426E-01	9.568E-02	2.288E-01	1.193E-01	6.394E-03	1.504E-01	5.268E-03	2.227E-01	1.392E-02
6.050E-01	2.425E-01	9.505E-02	2.250E-01	1.221E-01	6.630E-03	1.523E-01	5.550E-03	2.221E-01	1.422E-02
6.250E-01	2.394E-01	9.421E-02	2.254E-01	1.210E-01	6.891E-03	1.520E-01	5.800E-03	2.219E-01	1.440E-02
6.450E-01	2.417E-01	9.389E-02	2.233E-01	1.240E-01	6.989E-03	1.533E-01	5.952E-03	2.223E-01	1.468E-02
6.650E-01	2.399E-01	9.372E-02	2.215E-01	1.249E-01	7.086E-03	1.529E-01	6.087E-03	2.199E-01	1.480E-02
6.850E-01	2.383E-01	9.330E-02	2.218E-01	1.238E-01	7.193E-03	1.523E-01	6.179E-03	2.194E-01	1.470E-02
7.050E-01	2.386E-01	9.365E-02	2.197E-01	1.261E-01	7.140E-03	1.536E-01	6.165E-03	2.197E-01	1.479E-02
7.243E-01	2.395E-01	9.347E-02	2.207E-01	1.240E-01	7.186E-03	1.522E-01	6.178E-03	2.190E-01	1.464E-02
7.443E-01	2.468E-01	9.352E-02	2.194E-01	1.232E-01	7.158E-03	1.503E-01	6.179E-03	2.156E-01	1.453E-02
7.643E-01	2.507E-01	9.331E-02	2.207E-01	1.216E-01	7.159E-03	1.488E-01	6.157E-03	2.159E-01	1.454E-02
7.843E-01	2.537E-01	9.296E-02	2.219E-01	1.188E-01	7.213E-03	1.467E-01	6.175E-03	2.147E-01	1.428E-02
8.050E-01	2.607E-01	9.312E-02	2.212E-01	1.203E-01	7.127E-03	1.460E-01	6.136E-03	2.143E-01	1.423E-02
8.250E-01	2.626E-01	9.283E-02	2.229E-01	1.161E-01	7.197E-03	1.433E-01	6.168E-03	2.132E-01	1.393E-02
8.450E-01	2.626E-01	9.297E-02	2.227E-01	1.151E-01	7.232E-03	1.405E-01	6.238E-03	2.112E-01	1.399E-02
8.644E-01	2.761E-01	9.235E-02	2.276E-01	1.080E-01	7.329E-03	1.344E-01	6.302E-03	2.085E-01	1.377E-02
8.844E-01	2.870E-01	9.174E-02	2.289E-01	1.040E-01	7.476E-03	1.312E-01	6.409E-03	2.081E-01	1.347E-02
9.050E-01	2.862E-01	9.093E-02	2.339E-01	9.520E-02	7.776E-03	1.192E-01	6.794E-03	2.033E-01	1.348E-02
9.250E-01	2.883E-01	8.991E-02	2.387E-01	8.859E-02	7.997E-03	1.141E-01	6.977E-03	2.020E-01	1.335E-02
9.446E-01	2.774E-01	8.813E-02	2.463E-01	7.297E-02	8.439E-03	1.026E-01	7.332E-03	1.995E-01	1.295E-02
9.650E-01	2.704E-01	8.506E-02	2.568E-01	5.840E-02	8.875E-03	7.928E-02	7.979E-03	1.967E-01	1.283E-02
9.850E-01	2.551E-01	7.982E-02	2.709E-01	3.425E-02	9.551E-03	4.973E-02	8.803E-03	1.956E-01	1.249E-02
1.000E+00	2.175E-01	8.696E-02	3.237E-01	1.797E-02	1.161E-02	2.509E-02	1.097E-02	2.173E-01	1.431E-02

2.1.2. Nacelle and Tower

The detailed description of the nacelle and tower can be found in [1]. In QB, the nacelle and tower of the up-scaled SOFTWIND FOWT were modelled so that the total mass and centre of gravity of the RNA match the definition of the scaled model. The parameters of the nacelle are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Nacelle parameters of the SOFTWIND FOWT.

Parameter	Value
Hub mass	105520 kg
Nacelle mass	569032.5 kg
X-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	2.387 m
Y-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	0 m
Z-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	3.65 m
Distance tower top to shaft	10.6 m

The tower is made of an aluminium rod with an outer diameter of 2.4 m and an inner diameter of 2.24 m. The distributed parameters were obtained by appropriately scaling the density and Young’s modulus of the aluminium rod used in [1]. In addition, the stiffness was tuned to match the eigenfrequencies of the FOWT. The distributed tower properties are listed in Table 6 and Table 7.

Table 6: Tower structural properties of the SOFTWIND FOWT.

Norm. Length [-]	Mass Dens [kg/m ³]	Edge Stiff. [N m ²]	Flap Stiff. [N m ²]	Axial Stiff. [N]	Tors. Stiff. [N m ²]	Shear Stiff [N]	Struc. Pitch [deg]	Shear Factor X [-]
0.000E+00	1.590E+03	1.26E+12	1.260E+12	1.633E+12	8.798E+11	6.530E+11	0.000E+00	5.000E-01
1.000E+00	1.590E+03	1.26E+12	1.260E+12	1.633E+12	8.798E+11	6.530E+11	0.000E+00	5.000E-01

Table 7: Tower structural properties of the SOFTWIND FOWT (continued).

Norm. Length [-]	Shear Factor Y [-]	Rad. Gyr. X [-]	Rad. Gyr. Y [-]	Center Mass X [-]	Center Mass Y [-]	Center Elast. X [-]	Center Elast. Y [-]	Center Shear X [-]	Center Shear Y [-]
0.000E+00	5.000E-01	6.416E-01	6.416E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00
1.000E+00	5.000E-01	6.416E-01	6.416E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00

2.1.3. Substructure

The detailed definition of the substructure is again given in [1]. Within QB, the substructure is modelled as a rigid body using the linear potential flow with Morison drag (LPMD) approach [4]. The hydrodynamic radiation and diffraction coefficients were obtained from calculations using the software NEMOH [5]. The main parameters of the substructure are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Main parameters of the SOFWTIND FOWT substructure

Parameter	Value
Spar mass	$1.94 \cdot 10^7$ kg
Spar CoG (x,y,z) coordinates	(-0.16, 0, -71.56) m
Spar Rot. inertias around CoG (Ixx, Iyy, Izz)	($3.07 \cdot 10^{10}$, $3.07 \cdot 10^{10}$, $6.2 \cdot 10^9$) $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$
Additional mass of BG3 force transducer	$7.03 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Lower spar diameter	18.03 m
Upper spar diameter	11.2 m
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. for all members	0.3
Hydrodyn. axial drag coeff. for spar base	5.0

2.1.4. Mooring System

The mooring system of the SOFTWIND FOWT is made of chains connected in a delta-connection configuration [1]. This can be seen in Figure 1. Between the end of the delta connection and the mooring chain, there is a force transducer connected that measures the tension of the mooring lines. The main parameters of the mooring system modelled in QB are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Main parameters of the SOFTWIND FOWT mooring system.

Parameter	Value
Chain dry mass density	440 kg/m
Chain link diameter	0.148 m
Axial stiffness of chain element	$1.65 \cdot 10^9$ N
Anchor 1 (x,y) position	(638.4, -1.2) m
Anchor 2 (x,y) position	(-318.8, 554) m
Anchor 3 (x,y) position	(-320.4, -554.4) m
Effective chain diameter for hydrodyn. calcs.	0.266 m
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. for chain	1.0
Hydrodyn. normal added mass coeff. for chain	0.8

2.2. PRELIMINARY VALIDATION

In this section, the results of preliminary calculations to validate the behaviour of the model are presented. The full validation will be performed in separate study within WP2.

2.2.1. Frequency Calculations

The eigenfrequencies of the SOFTWIND model were calculated using the modal analysis tool within QB. Table 10 shows the comparison of the numerical and experimental eigenfrequencies of the FOWT. It can be seen that for the first fore-aft mode, the difference between the numerical model and the experiment is 1.8%. The difference increases for the second fore-aft mode, although the frequency of this eigenmode is well above the relevant frequencies of normal offshore wind turbine simulations.

Table 10: Comparison of numerical and experimental eigenfrequencies of the SOFTWIND FOWT.

Mode name	Value Experiment	Value QB
First FOWT side-side	N.A.	0.338 Hz
First FOWT fore-aft	0.382 Hz	0.376 Hz
Second FOWT fore-aft	4.68 Hz	5.01 Hz

The mode shape of the first FOWT fore-aft mode is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that it is a product of the coupling between the rotor, tower, substructure and mooring system.

Figure 3: Mode shape of the first fore-aft mode of the SOFTWIND FOWT in QB.

2.2.2. Decay Tests

The numerical model was also tested in three decay tests and compared to the experimental results. The same evaluation method – described in [6] – was used to process the time series of the experiments and the numerical simulations.

The results are shown in Figure 4. The matching of the eigenfrequencies is very good. There is some differences in the damping values though. It should be noted that the largest differences are seen in the linear damping. The absolute values of the linear damping were quite small and small absolute differences lead to large relative differences. It is believed that one source of the difference is the skin friction in the experiment, which is not modelled in QB and affects the small oscillations. This point still needs to be further analysed and will be cleared within WP2.

A qualitative inspection of the time series of the decay tests also reveals that the numerical model is able to match well the behaviour of the experiments in the considered degrees of freedom and other sensors. This can be seen in Figure 5 to Figure 7, where the time series of the three considered decay tests is shown. In these figures we can also see that the mooring line tension is around 5% higher in the QB model compared to the experiments. This difference is within the uncertainty of the experimental values. The differences in the surge DoF for the heave decay test (Figure 6) are small but noticeable. They come from the facts that the surge equilibrium positions were slightly different in each experimental decay test and that initial conditions of experimental tests were imposed with a small but non-zero velocity in surge. In QB, the same system equilibrium positions and initial conditions at rest are assumed. In Figure 6, it can also be seen that the large difference in the heave damping reported in Figure 4 is coming in from the small oscillations after 600 s in the time series. These are small oscillations that will not be relevant in the test cases with wind and waves in WP2.

Figure 4: Relative eigenfrequencies and dampings of the SOFTWIND FOWT decay tests.

Figure 5: Time series of the SOFTWIND surge decay test.

Figure 6: Times series of the SOFTWIND heave decay test.

Figure 7: Time series of the SOFTWIND pitch decay test.

2.3. PUBLIC LOCATION OF THE MODEL

The QB model of the SOFTWIND FOWT is publicly available at following location:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397358>

It should be noted that the model found on the abovementioned location might slightly deviate from the model described in this document. This is because further tuning of the numerical model might be necessary to better reflect the experimental results of the SOFTWIND campaign. All versions and changes to the model will be included in the abovementioned location.

3. DTU 10 MW RTW WITH HEXAFLOAT SUBSTRUCTURE

This section includes the model definition of the DTU 10 MW RWT with the Hexafloat substructure, along with the results of preliminary verification tests.

3.1. MODEL DEFINITION

The FOWT model consists of the RNA and tower of the DTU 10 MW RWT mounted on top of Saipem’s Hexafloat substructure. In this document, it will be named the Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT model. We give in this section the most important model parameters. Table 11 presents the main parameters of the FOWT and Figure 8 shows the model within QB.

Table 11: General parameters of the Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT.

Parameter	Value
Rated power	10 MW
Number of blades	3
Rotor diameter	178.3 m
Nominal hub height	132.5 m
Nominal draft	22.22 m
Rated rotor speed	9.6 rpm
Overhang	7.1 m
Shaft tilt angle	5 deg
Rotor pre-cone angle	2.5 deg
RNA mass	$6.77 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Tower mass	$6.287 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Substructure mass	$6.653 \cdot 10^7$ kg

Figure 8: The Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT aero-hydro-elastic model in QB.

3.1.1. Blade

The definition of the blade is the same as in Section 2.1.1, since both rotors are based on the DTU 10 MW RWT [2]. The aerodynamic and structural definitions of the blade are given in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. Similar to the SOFTWIND 10 MW FOWT model, a different aerodynamic discretization between blade definition and turbine model was used. The Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT blade is discretized in using 25 panels with a cosine spacing.

3.1.2. Nacelle and Tower

The detailed definition of the nacelle and tower is given in [2]. Table 12 presents the main parameters of the nacelle.

Table 12: Nacelle parameters of the Hexafloat FOWT.

Parameter	Value
Hub mass	105520 kg
Nacelle mass	446032.5 kg
X-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	2.687 m
Y-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	0 m

Z-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	2.45 m
Distance tower top to shaft	2.75 m

The structural properties of the tower are presented in Table 13 and Table 14.

Table 13: Tower structural properties of the Hexafloat FOWT.

Norm. Length [-]	Mass Dens. [kg/m³]	Edge Stiff. [N m²]	Flap Stiff. [N m²]	Axial Stiff. [N]	Tors. Stiff. [N m²]	Shear Stiff. [N]	Struc. Pitch [deg]	Shear Factor X [-]	Shear Factor Y [-]
0.000E+00	8.384E+03	1.767E+12	1.767E+12	2.071E+11	1.360E+12	7.966E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
9.946E-02	8.101E+03	1.595E+12	1.595E+12	2.002E+11	1.227E+12	7.698E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
9.946E-02	7.677E+03	1.512E+12	1.512E+12	1.897E+11	1.163E+12	7.295E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
1.989E-01	7.409E+03	1.359E+12	1.359E+12	1.831E+11	1.046E+12	7.040E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
1.989E-01	6.999E+03	1.285E+12	1.285E+12	1.729E+11	9.881E+11	6.651E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
2.984E-01	6.746E+03	1.150E+12	1.150E+12	1.667E+11	8.849E+11	6.411E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
2.984E-01	6.351E+03	1.084E+12	1.084E+12	1.569E+11	8.335E+11	6.035E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
3.978E-01	6.113E+03	9.663E+11	9.663E+11	1.510E+11	7.433E+11	5.809E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
3.978E-01	5.733E+03	9.066E+11	9.066E+11	1.416E+11	6.974E+11	5.447E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
4.973E-01	5.510E+03	8.049E+11	8.049E+11	1.361E+11	6.191E+11	5.235E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
4.973E-01	5.144E+03	7.519E+11	7.519E+11	1.271E+11	5.784E+11	4.888E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
5.967E-01	4.936E+03	6.642E+11	6.642E+11	1.219E+11	5.109E+11	4.690E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
5.967E-01	4.585E+03	6.173E+11	6.173E+11	1.133E+11	4.749E+11	4.356E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
6.962E-01	4.391E+03	5.425E+11	5.425E+11	1.085E+11	4.173E+11	4.173E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
6.962E-01	4.055E+03	5.012E+11	5.012E+11	1.002E+11	3.855E+11	3.853E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
7.956E-01	3.876E+03	4.379E+11	4.379E+11	9.576E+10	3.369E+11	3.683E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
7.957E-01	3.554E+03	4.018E+11	4.018E+11	8.781E+10	3.091E+11	3.377E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
8.951E-01	3.391E+03	3.488E+11	3.488E+11	8.377E+10	2.683E+11	3.222E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
8.951E-01	3.084E+03	3.175E+11	3.175E+11	7.618E+10	2.442E+11	2.930E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
1.000E+00	2.927E+03	2.714E+11	2.714E+11	7.231E+10	2.088E+11	2.781E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01

Table 14: Tower structural properties of the Hexafloat FOWT (continued).

Norm. Length [-]	Rad. Gyr. X [-]	Rad. Gyr. Y [-]	Center Mass X [-]	Center Mass Y [-]	Center Elast. X [-]	Center Elast. Y [-]	Center Shear X [-]	Center Shear Y [-]	Diameter [m]
0.000E+00	3.519E-01	3.519E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	8.30E+00
9.946E-02	3.519E-01	3.519E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	8.02E+00
9.946E-02	3.520E-01	3.520E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	8.02E+00
1.989E-01	3.519E-01	3.519E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	7.74E+00
1.989E-01	3.520E-01	3.520E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	7.74E+00
2.984E-01	3.519E-01	3.519E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	7.46E+00
2.984E-01	3.520E-01	3.520E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	7.46E+00
3.978E-01	3.520E-01	3.520E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	7.19E+00
3.978E-01	3.521E-01	3.521E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	7.19E+00
4.973E-01	3.520E-01	3.520E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.91E+00
4.973E-01	3.521E-01	3.521E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.91E+00
5.967E-01	3.521E-01	3.521E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.63E+00
5.967E-01	3.522E-01	3.522E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.63E+00

6.962E-01	3.521E-01	3.521E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.35E+00
6.962E-01	3.522E-01	3.522E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.35E+00
7.956E-01	3.522E-01	3.522E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.07E+00
7.957E-01	3.523E-01	3.523E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	6.07E+00
8.951E-01	3.522E-01	3.522E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	5.79E+00
8.951E-01	3.523E-01	3.523E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	5.79E+00
1.000E+00	3.523E-01	3.523E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	5.50E+00

3.1.3. Substructure

The substructure of the Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT is depicted in Figure 8. It consists of a floating hexagonal structure and a counterweight linked together with six tendons. In QB, the members of the substructure are modelled as flexible elements and the tendons as cable elements. The hydrodynamic forces are calculated using the Morison Equation (ME) approach in QB [4]. For the sake of brevity, only the main parameters of the substructure are presented here. The complete model definition can be found in Section 3.2.1. The general parameters of the substructure are listed in Table 15.

Table 15: General parameters of the Hexafloat FOWT substructure.

Parameter	Value
Floater mass	$2.434 \cdot 10^6$ kg
Floater CoG (x,y,z) coordinates	(0, 0, -15.98) m
Floater. rot. inertias around CoG (Ixx, Iyy, Izz)	$(1.30 \cdot 10^9, 1.30 \cdot 10^9, 2.30 \cdot 10^9)$ kg·m ²
Counter weight (CW) mass	$4.219 \cdot 10^6$ kg
CW CoG (x,y,z) coordinates	(0, 0, -147.0) m
CW rot. inertias around CoG (Ixx, Iyy, Izz)	$(3.483 \cdot 10^8, 3.483 \cdot 10^8, 2.676 \cdot 10^8)$ kg·m ²
Substructure CoG (x,y,z) coordinates	(0, 0, -86.87) m
Hydro. normal drag coeff. for floater members	0.6
Hydro. normal added mass coeff. for floater members	1.0
Hydro. normal drag coeff. for CW	0.52
Hydro. normal added mass coeff. for CW	0.55
Hydro. axial drag coeff. for CW	0.987
Hydro. axial added mass coeff. for CW	0.637

The members of the floater structure are made of steel tubes with a density of 7850 kg/m³ and a Young’s modulus of 210 GPa. The structural parameters for the flexible substructure members are given in Table 16 and Table 17.

Table 16: Structural properties of Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT substructure members.

Name	Mass Dens [kg/m ³]	Edge Stiff. [N m ²]	Flap Stiff. [N m ²]	Axial Stiff. [N]	Tors. Stiff. [N m ²]	Shear Stiff [N]	Struc. Pitch [deg]	Shear Factor X [-]	Shear Factor Y [-]
Main Col.	1.106E+04	2.515E+12	2.515E+12	2.959E+11	1.940E+12	1.141E+11	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
Tank	2.817E+03	1.819E+11	1.819E+11	7.537E+10	1.403E+11	2.907E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
Diag. Brace	1.481E+03	1.922E+10	1.922E+10	3.963E+10	1.483E+10	1.529E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01
Horiz. Brace	1.107E+03	1.447E+10	1.447E+10	2.961E+10	1.117E+10	1.142E+10	0.000E+00	5.000E-01	5.000E-01

Table 17: Structural properties of Hexafloat 10 MW FOWT substructure members (continued).

Name	Rad. Gyr. X [-]	Rad. Gyr. Y [-]	Center Mass X [-]	Center Mass Y [-]	Center Elast. X [-]	Center Elast. Y [-]	Center Shear X [-]	Center Shear Y [-]	Diameter [m]
Main Col.	3.512E-01	3.512E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	8.30E+00
Tank	3.515E-01	3.515E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	4.42E+00
Diag. Brace	3.482E-01	3.482E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	2.00E+00
Horiz. Brace	3.496E-01	3.496E-01	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	0.000E+00	2.00E+00

3.1.4. Mooring System

The mooring system of the Hexafloat FOWT is made of three chains connected to the floater. The main parameters of the mooring system modelled in QB are given in Table 18.

Table 18: Main parameters of the SOFTWIND FOWT mooring system.

Parameter	Value
Chain dry mass density	221 kg/m
Chain link diameter	0.105 m
Axial stiffness of chain element	$8.62 \cdot 10^8$ N
Anchor 1 (x,y) position	(-1061, 0) m
Anchor 2 (x,y) position	(529.03, -919) m
Anchor 3 (x,y) position	(529.03, 919) m
Effective chain diameter for hydrodyn. calcs.	0.21 m
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. for chain	1.2
Hydrodyn. normal added mass coeff. for chain	1.0

3.2. PRELIMINARY VALIDATION

3.2.1. Frequency Calculations

The eigenfrequencies of the Hexafloat model were again calculated in QB with the modal analysis tool. Table 19 shows the first four eigenfrequencies of the FOWT. The mode shapes of the first fore-aft and the second side-side mode are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, respectively.

Table 19: Eigenfrequencies of the first four modes of the Hexafloat FOWT.

Mode name	Value QB
First FOWT side-side	0.213 Hz
First FOWT fore-aft	0.213 Hz
Second FOWT fore-aft	0.566 Hz
Second FOWT side-side	0.576 Hz

A comparison of the FOWT eigenfrequencies with the Deeplines Wind™ model will be done in task 2.1 of WP2.

Figure 9: First FOWT fore-aft mode of the Hexafoat model.

Figure 10: Second FOWT side-side mode of the Hexafoat model.

3.2.2. Decay tests

The displacement eigenfrequencies of the numerical model were obtained by means of decay tests. The results are presented in Table 20. Again, the method described in [6] was used to obtain the damping values. These values are given as percentage of the critical damping. It should be noted that for all DoFs except yaw, the values for the linear damping are very close to 0%. This is because the Morison Equation hydrodynamic modelling approach used for this FOWT model only includes quadratic drag coefficients. The values obtained of the yaw DoF are unreliable, since the damping of this DoF was so high that only a handful of points were available to perform the linear regression and obtain the damping coefficients.

Table 20: Displacement eigenfrequencies and dampings of the Hexafloat FOWT.

DoF	Eigenfrequency	Lin. Damping	Quad. Damping
Surge	0.0044 Hz	-0.37%	77.86%
Sway	0.0044 Hz	-0.57%	80.14%
Heave	0.0278 Hz	0.19%	13.67%
Roll	0.0219 Hz	0.20%	7.94%
Pitch	0.0219 Hz	0.21%	8.32%
Yaw	0.0172 Hz	18.43%	-9.24%

The main DoFs of the individual decay tests can be seen in Figure 11. We can see that for the surge and sway decay tests, the time series show a superposition of multiple frequencies. It is believed that this comes from the interaction of the floater and counter weight of the Hexafloat substructure. Also, the strong damping of the yaw DOF mentioned before can be seen in this figure.

The detailed numerical comparison of the Hexafloat FOWT model between QB and Deeplines Wind™ will be part of WP 2.

Figure 11: Main DoFs of the Hexafloat FOWT decay tests.

3.3. PUBLIC LOCATION OF THE MODEL

The QB model of Hexafloat FOWT is publicly available at following location:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397313>

It should be noted that the model found on the abovementioned location might slightly deviate from the model described in this document. This is because further numerical tuning might be necessary to better align results in WP 2. All versions and changes to the model will be included in the abovementioned location.

4. OC5 5MW FLOATING WIND TURBINE

This section presents the definition of the QB model of the floating offshore wind turbine system analysed in the Offshore Code Comparison Collaboration, Continued, with Correlation (OC5) project [7]. The floating substructure is a semisubmersible type with close similarities to the floater analysed within Phase II of OC4 [8]. The turbine mounted on the floater is the MARIN stock wind turbine (MSWT) described in [9], a model-scale version of the NREL5-MW reference wind turbine [10] developed by the Maritime Research Institute Netherlands (MARIN) in 2013 [6]. The assembled FOWT-model was analysed experimentally in the MARIN offshore wave basin in a 1/50th scale. Both the model and the results are scaled up to full scale, which is why the full-scale turbine properties are used to build the model within QB.

4.1. MODEL DEFINITION

The detailed definition of the OC5 FOWT is provided in [6] and [7]. As for the other models described in this document, the most important aero-hydro-elastic properties of the OC5 FOWT model are provided. The fully assembled model in QB is illustrated in Figure 12. The main parameters are shown in Table 21.

Table 21: General parameters of the OC5 MARIN stock FOWT.

Parameter	Value
Rated power	5 MW
Number of blades	3
Rotor diameter	126 m
Nominal hub height	90 m
Nominal draft	20 m
Rated rotor speed	12.1 rpm
Overhang	10.6 m
Shaft tilt angle	0 deg
Rotor pre-cone angle	0 deg
RNA mass	$5.449 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Tower mass (incl. instrumentation)	$4.935 \cdot 10^5$ kg
Substructure total mass	$1.3019 \cdot 10^7$ kg

Figure 12: OC5 FOWT aero-hydro-elastic model in QB.

4.1.1. Blade

The rotor properties of the OC5 FOWT are based on the blade design detailed in [6] and [9]. The AG04 airfoil defines the aerodynamic behaviour along the entire span of the blade, aside from the cylindrical root sections. The blade may be treated as a stiff structure and apart from the cylindrical sections, a modified polar of the AG04 polar is used for all sections. This is in accordance with Goupeé et al. [9]. Table 22 shows the aerodynamic definition of the OC5 FOWT blade within QB. For the simulations, the blade was discretized using 18 aerodynamic panels with a cosine spacing.

Table 22: Aerodynamic blade definition of the OC5 FOWT

Position [m]	Chord [m]	Twist [deg]	IP Offset [m]	OOP Offset [m]	Airfoil
0	3.5	50.377	0	0	Cylinder
1.398	4.41	42.712	0	0	Cylinder
4.107	5.229	31.187	0	0	AG04 Cylinder Blend 1
6.816	5.581	23.109	0	0	AG04 Cylinder Blend 2
10.281	5.794	16.389	0	0	AG04 Cylinder Blend 3
14.376	5.796	11.475	0	0	AG04 Cylinder Blend 4
18.471	5.576	8.502	0	0	AG04 Cylinder Blend 5
22.566	5.297	6.523	0	0	AG04 Mod
26.661	5.006	5.052	0	0	AG04 Mod
30.756	4.706	3.878	0	0	AG04 Mod
34.851	4.392	2.939	0	0	AG04 Mod
38.946	4.078	2.216	0	0	AG04 Mod
43.041	3.775	1.673	0	0	AG04 Mod
47.136	3.48	1.245	0	0	AG04 Mod
51.231	3.19	0.844	0	0	AG04 Mod
54.696	2.914	0.497	0	0	AG04 Mod
57.405	2.651	0.235	0	0	AG04 Mod
60.114	1.747	0.064	0	0	AG04 Mod
61.5	0.05	0	0	0	AG04 Mod

To replicate the stiff behaviour of the experimental blade, the stiffness parameters below are multiplied by a factor of 10. The mass of the blade is achieved by reducing the “Mass Dens” column by the factor 0.9675. The remaining columns belong to the NREL5-MW blade but play a negligible role due to the increase in stiffness. The structural parameters of the blade are given in Table 23 and Table 24.

Table 23: Structural properties of the OC5 FOWT blade.

Norm. Length [-]	Mass Dens [kg/m ³]	Edge Stiff. [N m ²]	Flap Stiff. [N m ²]	Axial Stiff. [N]	Tors. Stiff. [N m ²]	Shear Stiff [N]	Struc. Pitch [deg]	Shear Factor X [-]
0.000E+00	1.01E+03	1.81E+10	1.81E+10	9.73E+09	5.56E+09	6.95E+08	0.00E+00	5.00E-01
4.800E-01	1.93E+02	1.81E+10	1.81E+10	9.73E+09	5.56E+09	6.95E+08	0.00E+00	5.00E-01
6.670E-01	9.04E+01	1.94E+10	1.96E+10	1.08E+10	5.43E+09	7.71E+08	0.00E+00	5.00E-01
1.000E+00	2.71E+02	1.75E+10	1.95E+10	1.01E+10	4.99E+09	7.19E+08	0.00E+00	5.00E-01

Table 24: Structural properties of the OC5 FOWT blade (continued).

Norm. Length [-]	Shear Factor Y [-]	Rad. Gyr. X [-]	Rad. Gyr. Y [-]	Center Mass X [-]	Center Mass Y [-]	Center Elast. X [-]	Center Elast. Y [-]	Center Shear X [-]	Center Shear Y [-]
0.000E+00	5.00E-01	3.29E-01	3.29E-01	-4.80E-05	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	0.00E+00	0.00E+0
4.800E-01	5.00E-01	3.29E-01	3.29E-01	-4.80E-05	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	0.00E+00	0.00E+0
6.670E-01	5.00E-01	3.27E-01	3.23E-01	7.01E-03	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	0.00E+0	0.00E+00	0.00E+0
1.000E+00	5.00E-01	3.06E-01	3.19E-01	3.89E-03	0.00E+0	5.50E-03	0.00E+0	5.50E-03	0.00E+0

4.1.2. Nacelle and Tower

In QB, the nacelle and tower of the up-scaled OC5-FOWT were modelled in accordance with the information provided in [6, 7]. The parameters of the nacelle are listed in Table 25.

Table 25: Nacelle Parameters of the SOFTWIND FOWT.

Parameter	Value
Hub mass	Integrated in Nacelle Mass
Nacelle mass	4.779E+05 kg
X-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	1.13 m
Y-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	0 m
Z-distance nacelle CoM from tower top	1.8 m
Distance tower top to shaft	1.8 m
RNA yaw inertia about CoM	8.5004E+07 kg · m ²

The tower is made of two sections of hollow aluminium rods. The bottom rod has an outer diameter of 1.683 m, an inner diameter of 1.27 m and a length of 12.065 m. The top rod fits into the bottom rod and has an outer diameter of 1.27 m, an inner diameter of 1.0285 m and a length of 64.95 m. An overlap between the tower rods exists so that the tower height of 78.2 m (including the yaw bearing) is matched. The distributed parameters were obtained by appropriately scaling the density and the Young's modulus of the aluminium rod. In addition to the tower properties, point masses representing measurement devices are distributed along the tower length in accordance with [6]. To match the documented tower mass including the weight caused by the measurement devices, a point mass of 64900 kg is added at 30% tower height. This position is chosen to properly match the CoM of the assembled FOWT and the eigenfrequencies in roll and pitch direction. To approximate the documented tower eigenfrequencies, the stiffness of the tower was scaled by the factor 0.85. The distributed tower properties are listed in Table 26 and Table 27.

Table 26: Tower structural properties of the OC5 FOWT.

Norm. Length [-]	Mass Dens [kg/m ³]	Edge Stiff. [N m ²]	Flap Stiff. [N m ²]	Axial Stiff. [N]	Tors. Stiff. [N m ²]	Shear Stiff [N]	Struc. Pitch [deg]	Shear Factor X [-]
0	2.66E+03	9.58E+11	9.58E+11	3.45E+12	1.33E+10	0	0	0
0.111956522	2.66E+03	9.58E+11	9.58E+11	3.45E+12	1.33E+10	0	0	0
0.111969309	3.87E+03	1.22E+12	1.22E+12	5.02E+12	1.69E+10	0	0	0
0.154283887	3.87E+03	1.22E+12	1.22E+12	5.02E+12	1.69E+10	0	0	0
0.154296675	1.21E+03	2.62E+11	2.62E+11	1.57E+12	3.64E+09	0	0	0
0.965473146	1.21E+03	2.62E+11	2.62E+11	1.57E+12	3.64E+09	0	0	0
0.965485934	0.00E+00	2.62E+11	2.62E+11	1.57E+12	3.64E+09	0	0	0
1	0.00E+00	2.62E+11	2.62E+11	1.57E+12	3.64E+09	0	0	0

Table 27: Tower structural properties of the OC5 FOWT (continued).

Norm. Length [-]	Shear Factor Y [-]	Rad. Gyr. X [-]	Rad. Gyr. Y [-]	Center Mass X [-]	Center Mass Y [-]	Center Elast. X [-]	Center Elast. Y [-]	Center Shear X [-]	Center Shear Y [-]	Diameter [m]
0	0	0.53	0.53	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.683
0.111956522	0	0.49	0.49	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.683
0.111969309	0	0.49	0.49	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.683
0.154283887	0	0.41	0.41	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.27
0.154296675	0	0.41	0.41	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.27
0.965473146	0	0.41	0.41	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.27
0.965485934	0	0.41	0.41	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.27
1	0	0.53	0.53	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0	0	1.683

4.1.3. Substructure

The detailed geometry of the OC5-definition of the substructure is also given in [6]. As for the SOFTWIND platform, the substructure is modelled as a rigid body using the LPMD approach [4]. The hydrodynamic radiation and diffraction coefficients were obtained from publicly available calculations with the software WAMIT [11].

In order to align with the documented draft of 20m, an additional weight of 100 000 kg is added to the floater (0.8 % of the total mass). The main parameters of the substructure are given in Table 28.

Table 28: Main parameters of the OC5 FOWT substructure

Parameter	Value
Semisub. mass	$1.3019 \cdot 10^7$ kg
Semisub. CoG (x,y,z) coordinates	(0, 0, -14.09) m
Semisub. Rot. inertias around CoG (Ixx, Iyy, Izz)	$(7.55 \cdot 10^9, 8.22 \cdot 10^9, 1.36 \cdot 10^{10})$ kg·m ²
Diameter main column	6.5 m
Diameter upper columns	12 m
Diameter base columns	24 m
Diameter cross braces	1.6 m
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. main column	0.56
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. upper column	0.61
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. base column	0.6
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. Cross braces	0.63
Hydrodyn. axial drag coeff. for all elements	3.85

4.1.4. Mooring System

The mooring system of the OC5-DeepCwind semisubmersible consists of three catenary mooring lines spread equidistantly around the Z-axis with one of mooring line being aligned with the X-axis of the platform [6]. The main parameters of the mooring system modelled in QB are given in Table 29.

Table 29: Main parameters of the OC5 FOWT mooring system.

Parameter	Value
Mooring line 1 dry mass density	125.6 kg/m
Mooring line 2 dry mass density	125.8 kg/m
Mooring line 3 dry mass density	125.4 kg/m
Mooring line 1 volume-equivalent diameter	0.1369 m
Mooring line 2 volume-equivalent diameter	0.1398 m
Mooring line 3 volume-equivalent diameter	0.1393 m
Mooring line 1 axial stiffness	$7.520 \cdot 10^8$ N
Mooring line 2 axial stiffness	$7.461 \cdot 10^8$ N
Mooring line 3 axial stiffness	$7.478 \cdot 10^8$ N
Anchor 1 (x,y) position	(418.8, 725.4) m
Anchor 2 (x,y) position	(-837.6, 0) m
Anchor 3 (x,y) position	(-418.8, -725.4) m
Hydrodyn. normal drag coeff. for chain	2.0
Hydrodyn. normal added mass coeff. for chain	0.8

4.2. PRELIMINARY VALIDATION

In this section, the results of preliminary calculations to validate the behaviour of the model are presented. The full validation will be performed in separate study within WP2.

4.2.1. Frequency Calculations

The eigenfrequencies of the OC5 FOWT model presented in Section 4.1 were calculated in a modal analysis within QB. Table 30 shows the comparison of the numerical and experimental eigenfrequencies of the FOWT. It can be seen that even though the stiffness of the tower was reduced substantially (see 4.1.2), the predicted eigenfrequencies in QB are about 7-8% higher compared to the ones obtained in the experimental campaign. A possible cause for this might be the connection point between the top and bottom rod. A request to the OC5 coordinator has been made and this problem will be addressed in the remainder of WP2

Table 30: Comparison of numerical and experimental eigenfrequencies of the SOFTWIND FOWT.

Mode name	Value Experiment	Value QB
First FOWT side-side	0.325 Hz	0.3470 Hz
First FOWT fore-aft	0.315 Hz	0.3415 Hz

Figure 13: Mode shape of the first fore-aft mode of the OC5 FOWT in QB.

The mode shape of the first FOWT fore-aft mode is shown in Figure 13. It can be seen that it is a product of the coupling of the rotor, tower, substructure and mooring system.

4.2.2. Static Tests

Figure 14: Cumulative mooring force of the OC5 FOWT in QB.

The mooring system of the OC5 FOWT model is validated in static load tests where the floater is traversed along the x-axis and the y-axis. The results can be seen in Figure 14, where good agreement with the experimental results are obtained. The respective forces in x and y direction are summed up across all mooring lines to obtain the total acting force along this axis.

4.2.3. Decay Tests

The numerical model was also simulated in decay tests and validated against the experimental results. The results are shown in Figure 15. As with the other two turbines, we used the method described in [6] to obtain the damping values. The matching of the eigenfrequencies is very good. There are some differences in the damping values, mainly in the linear damping of the surge and sway DoFs and the quadratic damping in the yaw DoF. These points still need to be further analysed and will be cleared within WP2.

The time series of the free decay tests from the OC5 experimental campaign are not publicly available. Therefore, a qualitative comparison of the time series cannot be made at this point. However, a request for this data has been made to the OC5 coordinator and we are confident to use this data to fine tune the model for the remainder of WP2.

Figure 15: Relative eigenfrequencies and dampings of the OC5 FOWT decay tests.

For the sake of completeness, the time series of the free decay test in all six DoFs are presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Time series of the OC5-FOWT decay tests in the principal DoFs.

4.3. PUBLIC LOCATION OF THE MODEL

The QB model of OC5 FOWT is publicly available at following location:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397352>

It should be noted that the model found on the abovementioned location might slightly deviate from the model described in this document. This is because further numerical tuning might be necessary to better align results in WP 2. All versions and changes to the model will be included in the abovementioned location.

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